

Roland C. Brautigam, 14 February 2022

Vaccines and Vaccine mandates: time for a different approach

The world is on fire due to political mandates based on vaccination status. Truckers in Canada blocking roads, Australia seeing one of its largest political demonstrations in history, Maori performing the Haka in front of Parliament in Wellington demanding freedom, French riot police clashing with protestors etc. The list is long. The demonstrations worldwide are taking place daily to end vaccine mandates, vaccine passports and other means of segregating vaccinated from unvaccinated with serious implications to many countries worldwide.

Recent data (1) from UK HSA suggest that people who have been vaccinated have strongly elevated chance of being infected with Covid 19's Omicron variant and/or get hospitalized and near zero efficacy to die from / with Covid19. Consequently one should stop immediately with vaccination and vaccination mandates for Covid19. A short analysis.

Since mid-January 2022 UK HSA in their weekly Vaccine Surveillance Reports compare people with "at least 3 doses" with unvaccinated people in their "overall table" showing relative cases per 100,000. Although UK HAS state in their disclaimer that these unadjusted data should not be used to determine efficacy, their argumentation for not doing so seems quite biased. Among others they state "*people who have never been vaccinated are more likely to have caught COVID-19 in the weeks or months before the period of the cases covered in the report. This gives them some natural immunity to the virus...*" This comment is important as it strengthens the case against vaccination, especially of previously infected people.

Data to determine efficacy should be found in the references provided in table 4. Unfortunately all references given/studies are either outdated (based on the Alpha, Beta or Delta variants), are undated, not peer-reviewed pre-prints, contain strong conflicts of interest by the author or a combination of all of the above. The raw unadjusted data is the best we have.

I will use three examples of the most recent Vaccine Surveillance Report Week 6 to demonstrate the significant negative effect the vaccines have to protect against Covid. For cases I use table 10 and 13, for presenting to emergency care I use table 11 and 13 and for death I use table 12 and 13.

Example 1: Cases 30-39 years infection

According to table 13 some 4.924/100,000 (4.9%) "at least 3 dose" were tested positive in the period between week 2 and week 5 of 2022. In the same table it mentions that 2.047/100,000 (2%) unvaccinated people tested positive in the same period suggesting that triple-vaccinated have a 250% higher chance of getting infected than unvaccinated but in order to determine a level of efficacy ALL vaccinated persons need to be compared against unvaccinated. According to table 10 some 196,728 triple vaccinated persons of this age group tested positive more than 14 days after the booster shot, some 117,701 double vaccinated >14 days after their 2nd shot, 14,983 single dosed >21 days after their 1st shot and 1,734 one dose < 21 days after their 1st dose. This is a total of 331,146 vaccinated 30-39 year but we do not know how many vaccinated tested positive within the 14 resp 21 days after their shot. If

they are in the “unlinked” group then no problem for the calculations but if they are categorized as “unvaccinated” this would present a problem.

The percentage of 4.9% triple vaccinated is based on the 196.728 mentioned in table 10. If we extrapolate 196.728 to 331.146 we need to use a factor of 1.68. Extrapolating 4.924 with 1.68 results in 7.768 (7.4%) vaccinated vs 2.047 (2%) unvaccinated.

Negative efficacy therefore some 380%

Vaccinated people seem to have nearly 4 times higher chance of getting infected with Covid than unvaccinated people of age 30-39 years in England between week 2 and 5 2022.

Example 2: 18-29 years hospitalization

The argument towards the end of 2021 from various health authorities around the world shifted from “protect yourself and protect others” to “not so good against infection but highly effective against hospitalization and death”.

Using table 11 and table 13 we see 5.1/100.000 (0.005%) triple vaccinated 18-29 year olds are admitted to emergency care compared to 9.3 (0.009%) unvaccinated. These percentages are based on the data in table 11 which read 165 cases for triple vaccinated and 282 for unvaccinated. Of course, again to calculate efficacy we need to add all vaccinated people in this group and then compare them to the unvaccinated. Adding single dosed 103 and double dosed (270 cases) the total becomes 538 vaccinated compared to 282 unvaccinated. Again, these exclude any positive cases within the 14 resp 21 days from specimen date.

Extrapolating 165 to 538 requires a factor 3.2. If we extrapolate 0.0051% by a factor 3.2 the result is 0.016% vs 0.009% for the unvaccinated

Negative efficacy against emergency care reporting for vaccinated versus unvaccinated 18 to 29 years olds in week 2 and week 5 2022 was minimum 78%.

This excludes the <14 resp <21 days for vaccinated people

Example 3: 40-49 years death

Table 13 mentions 0.7/100.000 (0.0007%) triple dosed died in week 2 to 5 2022 in the age group 40-49 based on 34 deaths with 3 doses > 14 days after specimen date against 39 unvaccinated translating into 2.4/100.000 (0.0024%) suggesting some 75% efficacy of triple vaccinated versus unvaccinated.

However if we add the 12 single dosed and 39 double dosed we come to 85 vaccinated against 39 unvaccinated

Extrapolating 34 to 85 requires a factor 2.5. If we multiply 0.0007% with 2.5 it results in 0.0018% versus 0.0024% - an efficacy of maximum 25%. Again we miss the data for the vaccinated people in this age group who died with a positive test within the 14 resp 21 days from specimen date.

25% efficacy is well insufficient for continuation of the emergency market authorization issued by the EMA and nowhere near UK HAS's own estimate of 75% after booster for Omicron

The tables for the vaccinated group include only cases where the relevant dose was received 14 resp 21 days following the specimen date. Cases where the patient tested positive within 14 or 21 days following their dose are excluded. This is a critical problem according to Hullinghurst et al (6) as it suggests a very large group of cases, hospitalisations and deaths are not included in the vaccinated group. Their results showed “...observed a small proportion of care home residents with positive polymerase chain reaction (tests following vaccination 1.05% (N = 148), with 90% of infections occurring within 28 days.” If we would only add 10% of the vaccinated cases < 14 days to example 3, the vaccine efficacy shifts to negative.

These findings are confirmed by the statistics of the weekly Surveillance Reports issued by NSW Health (7)(see table 4). According to the latest data people with “no effective dose” have a 1.1% chance of being hospitalised, 0.1% chance of going to the ICU and 0.1% chance of dying from Omicron.

However double vaccinated show 1.2% vs hospitalisation, 0.1% vs ICU and 0.1% vs death. Triple dosed show 1.5% vs hospitalisation, 0.1% vs ICU and 0.1% vs death. Single dosed people have even more dramatic percentages at 2.7%, 0,3% and 0.3%.

Not only do people with “no effective dose” have a lower chance of hospitalisation and no elevated chance of ICU and death, “no effective” dose in fact includes people who have had their first dose less than 21 days prior to infection. The true number of “fully unvaccinated” is therefore potentially substantially lower further reducing the chance of infection, hospital, IC or death for this group. It is questionable at least why NSW Health will not release the data of the fully unvaccinated in their weekly reports.

In my earlier paper about vaccine efficacy “A critical review: efficacy of Covid19 vaccines depend largely on accuracy of VAERS reporting system” (2) I suggested that for a vaccine which does not prove to provide immunity, reported side effects for infection, hospitalization or death due to vaccination need to be added to the case numbers of the vaccinated to determine efficacy. Since it is clear that the Covid19 vaccines to say the least offer no immunity we need to add the reported side effects under the yellow card system in the UK during the period of week 2 to week 5 in 2022.

Since the beginning of vaccination following side effects were reported:

- 442.350 reports
- 1.149.009 reactions
- 1972 deaths

On average this accounts to 5 reported deaths per day from 1128 serious reports per day. According to MHRA these reports are mostly in the elderly with underlying disease but this is actually incorrect according to their own data (3) where the vast majority of reports is in the age group below 60, some 75-80%.

The booster campaign started 21 December 2022 in the UK and since then some 20.247 reports have been issued, 368 per day on average.

We don't have the data for week 2 until 5 of 2022 in the various age groups but based on historic data it is evident that by merely adding a very small proportion of cases to the infections, E&R and deaths either the already negative efficacy becomes more catastrophic or moves from a small positive efficacy to a serious negative efficacy. For example 3 which states 85 vaccinated deaths in a one week period, only adding 2 daily reported vaccine deaths would result in near zero efficacy.

Conclusion: with the introduction of Omicron, a variant which reportedly is 75-90% less virulent than Delta (4) we see very serious negative efficacy in Covid19 vaccines with substantial increased risk of infection, hospitalization and death for vaccinated people over unvaccinated people. In addition the vaccine adverse effects add further increased risk making current vaccination against Omicron ineffective and harmful. Additionally long term effects are still unknown, so are risks to people with autoimmune disorders and immune compromised people (5).

Based on these findings the vaccination campaign must be halted and all mandates based on vaccination status stopped immediately.

References:

- 1) https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1054071/vaccine-surveillance-report-week-6.pdf
- 2) <https://zenodo.org/record/5535837#.YVURdJpBz-j>
- 3) https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1054481/Coronavirus_vaccine_-_summary_of_Yellow_Card_reporting_2_2_22.pdf
- 4) <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35085225/>
- 5) https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/documents/rmp-summary/comirnaty-epar-risk-management-plan_en.pdf (module 7)
- 6) <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34850818/>
- 7) <https://www.health.nsw.gov.au/Infectious/covid-19/Pages/weekly-reports.aspx>

Tables for Examples from Vaccine Surveillance Report Week 6 (1):

Table 1: Table 10 infection

COVID-19 vaccine surveillance report - week 6

Table 13. Unadjusted rates of COVID-19 infection, hospitalisation and death in vaccinated and unvaccinated populations. Please note that the following table should be read in conjunction with pages 35 to 39 of this report, and the footnotes provided on page 44.

	Cases reported by specimen date between week 2 2022 (w/e 16 January 2022) and week 5 2022 (w/e 6 February 2022)		Cases presenting to emergency care (within 28 days of a positive test) resulting in overnight hospital admission, by specimen date between week 2 2022 (w/e 16 January 2022) and week 5 2022 (w/e 6 February 2022)		Death within 28 days of positive COVID-19 test by date of death between week 2 2022 (w/e 16 January 2022) and week 5 2022 (w/e 6 February 2022)		Death within 60 days of positive COVID-19 test by date of death between week 2 2022 (w/e 16 January 2022) and week 5 2022 (w/e 6 February 2022)	
	Unadjusted rates among persons vaccinated with at least 1 dose (per 100,000)*	Unadjusted rates among persons not vaccinated (per 100,000)**	Unadjusted rates among persons vaccinated with at least 1 dose (per 100,000)*	Unadjusted rates among persons not vaccinated (per 100,000)**	Unadjusted rates among persons vaccinated with at least 1 dose (per 100,000)*	Unadjusted rates among persons not vaccinated (per 100,000)**	Unadjusted rates among persons vaccinated with at least 1 dose (per 100,000)*	Unadjusted rates among persons not vaccinated (per 100,000)**
Under 18	1,879.3	8,888.8	4.2	14.5	0.0	8.1	0.0	8.1
18 to 29	3,349.7	1,885.8	5.1	9.5	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.6
30 to 39	4,504.2	2,047.8	6.4	11.8	0.2	0.9	0.3	1.3
40 to 49	4,687.3	1,758.8	9.9	11.0	0.7	2.4	0.8	3.4
50 to 59	2,054.5	1,187.8	7.9	21.6	1.2	6.8	1.7	12.5
60 to 69	1,824.8	196.7	11.2	29.3	4.3	29.6	5.8	37.3
70 to 79	1,200.7	645.4	26.5	156.2	14.8	90.3	17.6	104.1
80 or over	1,415.6	883.8	85.3	271.6	86.6	297.8	102.8	303.5

*Comparing case rates among vaccinated and unvaccinated populations should not be used to estimate vaccine effectiveness against COVID-19 infection. Vaccine effectiveness has been formally estimated from a number of different sources and is summarised on pages 4 to 15 in this report. The rates are calculated per 100,000 in people who have received either 1 dose of a COVID-19 vaccine or in people who have not received a COVID-19 vaccine. These figures are updated each week as the number of unvaccinated individuals and individuals vaccinated with 1 dose in the population changes. The case rates in the unvaccinated and unvaccinated populations are unadjusted rates that do not take into account individual-level factors for the date and these are likely to be overestimated.

COVID-19 vaccine surveillance report - week 6

Table 10. COVID-19 cases by vaccination status between week 2 2022 and week 5 2022. Please note that corresponding rates by vaccination status can be found in Table 13.

Cases reported by specimen date between week 2 2022 (w/e 16 January 2022) and week 5 2022 (w/e 6 February 2022)	Total	Unlinked*	Not vaccinated	Received one dose (1 to 20 days before specimen date)	Received one dose, ≥21 days before specimen date	Second dose ≥14 days before specimen date ¹	Third dose ≥14 days before specimen date ¹
Under 18	749,606	37,055	567,233	7,039	112,432	24,523	1,324
18 to 29	332,919	30,570	57,354	2,590	19,531	115,218	107,656
30 to 39	413,170	26,415	55,609	1,734	14,983	117,701	196,728
40 to 49	349,236	18,681	28,128	670	7,047	68,341	226,369
50 to 59	220,512	12,073	11,561	237	2,665	28,093	165,883
60 to 69	119,239	6,986	4,212	96	1,048	8,805	98,092
70 to 79	63,468	3,856	1,544	37	473	3,010	54,548
80 or over	45,621	4,808	1,188	14	490	3,604	35,517

[This data should be interpreted with caution. See information below in footnote about the correct interpretation of these figures]

* Individuals whose NHS numbers were unavailable to link to the NIMS. In the context of very high vaccine coverage in the population, even with a highly effective vaccine, it is expected that a large proportion of cases, hospitalisations and deaths would occur in vaccinated individuals, simply because a larger proportion of the population are vaccinated than unvaccinated and no vaccine is 100% effective. This is especially true because vaccination has been prioritised in individuals who are more susceptible or more at risk of severe disease. Individuals in risk groups may also be more at risk of hospitalisation or death due to non-COVID-19 causes, and thus may be hospitalised or die with COVID-19 rather than because of COVID-19.

COVID-19 vaccine surveillance report – week 6

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40 to 49	349,236	18,681	28,128	670	7,047	68,341	226,369
50 to 59	220,512	12,073	11,561	237	2,665	28,093	165,883
60 to 69	119,239	6,986	4,212	96	1,048	8,805	98,092
70 to 79	63,468	3,856	1,544	37	473	3,010	54,548
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Table 2: Table 11: E&R reporting

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Table 11. COVID-19 cases presenting to emergency care (within 28 days of a positive specimen) resulting in an overnight inpatient admission by vaccination status between week 2 2022 and week 5 2022

Please note that corresponding rates by vaccination status can be found in Table 13.

Cases presenting to emergency care (within 28 days of a positive test) resulting in overnight inpatient admission, by specimen date between week 2 2022 (w/e 16 January 2022) and week 5 2022 (w/e 6 February 2022)	Total	Unlinked*	Not vaccinated	Received one dose (1 to 20 days before specimen date)	Received one dose, ≥21 days before specimen date	Second dose ≥14 days before specimen date ¹	Third dose ≥14 days before specimen date ¹
Under 18	1,734	47	1,524	5	126	29	3
18 to 29	844	24	282	10	93	270	165
30 to 39	989	10	320	6	74	325	254
40 to 49	816	10	189	4	64	262	287
50 to 59	987	22	216	8	46	257	438
60 to 69	1,135	7	208	6	41	242	631
70 to 79	1,838	7	254	5	49	319	1,204
80 or over	2,854	5	268	2	68	417	2,094

* Individuals whose NHS numbers were unavailable to link to the NIMS.

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Table 3) table 12 – death within 28 days

COVID-19 vaccine surveillance report – week 6

Table 12. COVID-19 deaths (a) within 28 days and (b) within 60 days of positive specimen or with COVID-19 reported on death certificate, by vaccination status between week 2 2022 and week 5 2022

Please note that corresponding rates by vaccination status can be found in Table 13.

(a)

Death within 28 days of positive COVID-19 test by date of death between week 2 2022 (w/e 16 January 2022) and week 5 2022 (w/e 6 February 2022)	Total**	Unlinked*	Not vaccinated	Received one dose (1 to 20 days before specimen date)	Received one dose, ≥21 days before specimen date	Second dose ≥14 days before specimen date ¹	Third dose ≥14 days before specimen date ¹
[This data should be interpreted with caution. See information below in footnote about the correct interpretation of these figures]							
Under 18	11	0	7	0	2	2	0
18 to 29	28	1	12	0	1	9	5
30 to 39	62	1	24	0	4	25	8
40 to 49	125	1	39	0	12	39	34
50 to 59	304	6	97	1	23	101	76
60 to 69	619	5	156	1	22	204	231
70 to 79	1289	5	216	4	39	360	665
80 or over	3,540	13	360	2	97	891	2,177

* Individuals whose NHS numbers were unavailable to link to the NIMS.

** number of deaths of people who had had a positive test result for COVID-19 and either died within 60 days of the first positive test or have COVID-19 mentioned on their death certificate.

¹ In the context of very high vaccine coverage in the population, even with a highly effective vaccine, it is expected that a large proportion of cases, hospitalisations and deaths would occur in vaccinated individuals, simply because a larger proportion of the population are vaccinated than unvaccinated and no vaccine is 100% effective. This is especially true because vaccination has been prioritised in individuals who are more susceptible or more at risk of severe disease. Individuals in risk groups may also be more at risk of hospitalisation or death due to non-COVID-19 causes, and thus may be hospitalised or die with COVID-19 rather than because of COVID-19.

Table 4 – NSW Surveillance Report week 3 in 2022

Table 5. Hospitalisations, ICU admissions and deaths among PCR confirmed cases diagnosed with COVID-19, by vaccination status, NSW, from 26 November 2021 to 22 January 2022

Vaccination status	Total cases	Hospitalised* (% of total cases)	Hospitalised and in ICU* (% of total cases)	Death* (% of total cases)
Three or more effective doses	23,782	366 (1.5%)	31 (0.1%)	22 (0.1%)
Two effective doses	438,255	5,137 (1.2%)	439 (0.1%)	287 (0.1%)
One effective dose	5,521	150 (2.7%)	19 (0.3%)	14 (0.3%)
No effective dose	72,772	822 (1.1%)	93 (0.1%)	98 (0.1%)
Under investigation	129,604	1,833 (1.4%)	212 (0.2%)	15 (<0.1%)
Total	669,934	8,308 (1.2%)	794 (0.1%)	436 (0.1%)

*Note: Table categories are not mutually exclusive. Hospitalised includes cases admitted to ICU; deaths may occur with or without being admitted to hospital or ICU.

Table 6. Proportion of PCR confirmed cases with a severe outcome (ICU and/or death) amongst all cases, by age, time of infection, and vaccination status, NSW, 26 November 2021 to 22 January 2022

Age-group (years)	Three or more effective doses	Two effective doses	Less than two effective doses
0-9	-	-	<1% (15 / 54,536)
10-19	0% (0 / 232)	<1% (5 / 54,508)	<1% (6 / 15,854)
20-29	<1% (1 / 3,849)	<1% (22 / 128,000)	<1% (7 / 2,692)
30-39	<1% (2 / 3,833)	<1% (33 / 87,486)	1% (11 / 2,123)
40-49	<1% (2 / 5,125)	<1% (38 / 64,157)	1% (14 / 1,176)
50-59	<1% (5 / 4,258)	<1% (58 / 52,112)	3% (22 / 687)
60-69	<1% (10 / 2,911)	<1% (106 / 31,310)	6% (33 / 512)
70-79	1% (15 / 2,081)	1% (189 / 14,013)	9% (33 / 379)
80-89	1% (8 / 1,046)	3% (160 / 5,373)	17% (40 / 231)
90+	2% (7 / 447)	5% (63 / 1,296)	17% (18 / 103)
Total	<1% (50 / 23,782)	<1% (674 / 438,255)	<1% (199 / 78,293)

* Less than two effective doses combines those with one and no effective dose.

- In the past week, 71,217 (64.5%) of all PCR confirmed cases had received at least two effective doses (see Appendix C), reflective of the high proportion of community vaccination (90.0% of those aged 12 years and over, at the start of this wave on 26 November 2021). Similar breakdowns by vaccination status for previous periods are in Appendix C.
- The proportion of cases who were hospitalised, admitted to ICU or died is similar in Table 5 for those with no effective dose and those with two effective doses because the no effective dose group contains a very large proportion of young children, who typically have mild outcomes and are only very rarely hospitalised, admitted to ICU or die. Likewise, the overall rate of hospitalisation, ICU admission and death is presently similar for those with three effective doses compared to those with two effective doses, because the group with three effective doses contains a larger proportion of elderly cases, as well as more people with immunosuppression, who were eligible for a third vaccine dose earlier. Therefore, it is important to consider rates of hospitalisation, ICU admission, and death by age group as well as vaccination status. Table 6 and Appendix C show such further breakdowns by age range.
- In the period since 26 November 2021, the number of cases with two effective doses who experience severe outcomes is reflective of the high number in the community who have received two effective doses. However, the proportion of cases with two effective doses who experience severe outcomes is still lower than that for cases with less than two effective doses in every age group, demonstrating the effectiveness of vaccines to protect against severe outcomes.
- Caution should be used when interpreting rates among people over 60 with less than two effective doses since 26 November 2021. The denominator among cases is small, because the proportion of people in the community aged over 60 with no effective dose is small.
- Caution should also be used when interpreting rates among those with three or more effective doses, as the number who have received three doses is still relatively small. Rates will become more reliable as a greater proportion of the population receives their third dose. However, the preliminary evidence to date suggests that three or more effective doses provides additional protection against ICU admission and/or death, compared to having received only two effective doses.